
D4.3 Specifications for developing an EPC translating tool

Task 4.2 Adapting EPCs to user and investor needs

WP4 Increasing the value of EPCs

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Date: 21/03/2025

crossCert: Cross Assessment of Energy Certificates in Europe

Grant Agreement (GA) No: 101033778

From 1 Sept. 2021 to 31 Aug. 2024

H2020-LC-SC3-2018-2019-2020 / H2020-LC-SC3-EE-2020-2

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101033778

DELIVERABLE FACTSHEET

Document title	Specifications for developing an EPC translating tool
Deliverable	D4.3
Responsible Partner	REGEA
Contributors	All crossCert partners
Reviewers	MIEMA
Work Package	WP4
Task	4.2
Version	7.0
Version date	21/03/2025
Type of deliverable	R

Dissemination level	
X	PU = Public
	CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)

Document status		
Review status	<input type="checkbox"/>	Draft
	<input type="checkbox"/>	WP leader accepted
Action requested	X	Coordinator accepted
	<input type="checkbox"/>	To be revised by partners
	<input type="checkbox"/>	For approval by the WP leader
	<input type="checkbox"/>	For approval by the Project Coordinator
	X	To be delivered to the Commission

Document History

Version	Date	Main modification	Entity
1.0	14/06/2024	First draft to partners for comments	REGEA
2.0	14/06/2024	Received comments from coordinator	UNIZAR
3.0	03/07/2024	Corrected according to coordinator comments	REGEA
4.0	04/07/2024	Distributed to partners for comments	UNIZAR
5.0	18/07/2024	Corrected according to partners comments	REGEA
6.0	22/07/2024	Version ready for delivery	UNIZAR
7.0	21/03/2025	Version revised after Final report submission	REGEA

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is the result of work performed in Task 4.2 Adapting EPCs to user and investor needs within WP4 Increasing the value of EPCs. It outlines the specifications for developing an EPC (Energy Performance Certificate) translating tool aimed at simplifying EPC data for non-technical users and investors, thereby increasing the value and acceptance of EPCs. The tool will convert complex EPC data into easily understandable information, considering variations in national energy certificate designs and calculation processes, and incorporating findings from various related research projects.

The main objectives of the tool could be summarized as follows:

- **Enhanced EPC usability:** To bridge the gap between technical EPC data and the understanding of average users and investors, fostering wider acceptance and action.
- **Data translation:** To convert complex EPC parameters into simpler, investor-friendly metrics.
- **Standardization and customization:** To accommodate variations in EPC design and calculation processes across different European nations while providing personalized recommendations.
- **Alignment with EU legislation:** To comply with DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1275, ensuring EPCs effectively communicate energy performance and promote building renovations.

The inability of the typical EPC owner or user to grasp the statistics and parameters provided in the EPC due to a lack of technical knowledge is one of the primary obstacles to a wider acceptance of EPCs by end users. The current energy certificates need to have their key features taken out and modified so that non-professional users may readily grasp them in order to improve the EPC user experience. This deliverable focuses on generating the specifications and criteria needed to create a tool that will translate data from the current EPCs into simpler, easier-to-understand terminology. The requirements for creating such a tool considered variations in each partner nation's energy certificate design and calculating process. WP2, WP3, and WP5 outcomes have been taken into consideration when developing the specification.

The report is organized into three main sections:

1. Input data: Standardized information collected from various EPC assessments across member states of the EU, including methodologies from previous deliverables (D3.1, D3.2, D2.5), encompassing EPC assessment approaches, performance gap causation and cross-testing data. This includes building characteristics, energy consumption data and technical system specifications.

D2.5 highlighted the lack of EU-wide standardization in EPCs, the need for standardized calculation methodologies for comparing buildings, and the importance of building-specific models for effective renovation recommendations.

D3.1 and D3.2 emphasized variations in EPC evaluation techniques across Europe and the need to address performance gaps between calculated and actual energy consumption.

Variations in how EPCs are calculated and the types of metrics presented by different countries are summarized. For example, differences in methodologies across Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, and others highlight the need for harmonization in measuring energy performance.

2. Output data: Easily interpretable results intended to attract investors, extracted from deliverables (D3.3, D2.6, D5.1, D5.2), including new scales, KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) and end-user survey results. Output prioritizes clarity and actionable insights.

D2.6 highlighted that New EPC approaches should focus on user-friendly formats, online tools, and integration of Smart Readiness Indicators (SRI).

D3.3 Identified key performance indicators (KPIs) related to smartness, human-centric factors, energy performance, financial parameters, and climate change. Stressed the importance of balancing technical data with user-friendly presentation, potentially through infographics and clear explanations.

D5.1 & D5.2 Revealed that existing EPCs are often too complex and lack context for general users. Recommended improved design, visual representation, and contextualization with relatable information (e.g., financial benefits, comparisons). Users prefer multi-page documents with various data presentation modes and online resources.

New scales and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are discussed, emphasizing the need for user-friendly data presentation. The report notes that metrics should focus primarily on energy performance, carbon emissions, and financial implications to increase their relevance to end users. A consideration of EU regulations and directives (e.g., Directive (EU) 2024/1275) shaping future EPC frameworks outlines requirements for improved clarity and functionality in communicating energy efficiency.

3. EPC translating tool: An interactive web application that converts input data into output data, providing users with clear recommendations and cost-effective renovation strategies. Specifications are detailing how the tool will function, including user interface requirements, algorithm suggestions and user account management.

The proposed algorithm involves a two-step process:

1. Data input: Gathering building information, energy consumption data, and technical system details from EPCs, energy audits, and building owners.
2. Data output: Analyzing building data and generating recommendations for energy efficiency improvements, including cost estimates, energy savings potential, and CO2 emission reductions.

The analysis resulted with following technical specifications for EPC translating tool:

- Platform: Web-based application accessible via standard web browsers.
- User accounts: Hierarchical user access levels (Administrator, Main Manager, Manager) with varying permissions for data input, editing, and review.
- Building data entry: Two-tiered data entry system (simple and complex) to accommodate varying levels of available information.
- Energy efficiency measures: Calculation of cost-effective combinations of measures, including thermal insulation, window/door replacement, heating system upgrades (e.g., condensing boilers, heat pumps), ventilation systems, and renewable energy installations (solar thermal, photovoltaic).
- Results presentation: Tabular and graphical representation of results, highlighting the most cost-effective RES (Renewable Energy Sources) and EnU (Energy Use) measures. Data exportable in Excel, Word, or PDF formats.
- Support: Comprehensive user and technical documentation, including a "help" button on each user interface.

The EPC translating tool represents a significant step towards making energy performance data more accessible and actionable. By simplifying complex information and providing clear recommendations, the tool will empower building owners and investors to make informed decisions about energy efficiency improvements, contributing to a more sustainable built environment. The tool's success hinges on its user-friendliness, data accuracy, and alignment with relevant regulations and standards.

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1 Introduction

The following deliverables' findings served as the foundation for this one:

- D2.5 Cross testing data from existing EPCs
- D2.6 Cross testing of first generation of new EPCs
- D3.1 Review of approaches to EPC assessment across chosen member states,
- D3.2 Performance gap causation
- D3.3 Analysis of new scales and KPIs
- D5.1 Report on existing attitudes, expectations and needs
- D5.2 Survey and workshop results of EPC end-users

The aim of this report is to provide clear connection from technical parameters contained in energy performance certificate which general user does not perceive understandable and relevant to user-friendly parameters that will motivate the user to focus on recommendations provided and decide to invest in deep renovation of his building.

The document's first section focuses on the EPC translation tool's input data, which was taken from D3.1, D3.2, and D2.5. These documents will be analysed to standardise input data and offer an example algorithm for the EPC translating tool. The comparison of inputs for partner nations methodology, metrics provided in each country's EPC, indicators, and scales of EPCs in the crossCert countries will be done from these documents.

The second section of the text focuses on the output data, which is data that is easy to use and is taken from D3.3, D2.5, D5.1, and D5.2 in order to motivate investors. To provide ideal outputs for the EPC translation tool, new scales, KPIs, and cross-testing data from the first generation of new EPCs will be analysed from these papers.

The document's third section focuses on the EPC translation tool itself, offering a description, technical specifications, and programming choices to help regular users maximise the value of their certificates.

2 Input data

2.1 D3.1 (Review of approaches to EPC assessment across chosen member states) results

D3.1 *Review of approaches to EPC assessment across chosen member states* focuses on examining both broad and specific elements of EPC evaluation techniques. It provides an overview of EPC approaches that are currently being used in selected European nations, with an emphasis on those that are pertinent to the crossCert initiative. The data gathered serves as a point of reference for this research, highlighting variations in methods for conducting energy assessments and, consequently, variations in reactions to the Energy Performance in Buildings Directive. EPC techniques are categorised in D3.1 according to the kind of calculation methodology employed, the ways in which input data is gathered, the usage of actual building and/or energy data, and the outputs that are produced during the EPC process. This classification facilitates research into the effects of EPC decisions made at the national level on EPC outputs and any ramifications resulting from these outputs. Table 1 and Figure 1 present the findings.

Table 1. Comparison of inputs for partner countries methodologies

Comparison of inputs for partner countries methodologies					
Country	Austria	Bulgaria	Croatia	Denmark	Greece
HVAC schedules	Default (based on building type)	Assessor	Default (based on building type)	Assessor	Default (based on zone activity type)
HVAC specification	Default values available	Actual values	Default values available	Default values available	Default values available
Lighting and equipment schedules	Default values	Assessor	Default values or assessor	Default values	Default values
Occupancy schedules	Default values (mandatory)	Assessor	Default values (mandatory)	Default values (mandatory)	Default values (mandatory)
Construction thermal parameters	Database available	Database available	Database available	Database available	Database available
Building envelope U-values	Database available	Assessor	Database available	Database available	Database available
Ventilation rates	Database available	Measurement/Assessors knowledge	Database available	Database available	Database available
Infiltration rate	Default values available	Measurement/Assessors knowledge	Default values available	Default values available	Default values available
Temperature setpoints	Default values/Fixed	Assessor	Depends on use type/activity level/control	Default values/Fixed	Depends on use type/activity level/control/ different for heating and cooling season
Basic education	Engineers/Architects/Technical professionals	Technical education with 6 years' experience/ University degree with 2-3 years' experience	Technical education with 10 years' experience/ University degree with 5 years' experience	EQF level 4 technical education	Engineers/Architects

Asset/Operational rating	Asset rating	Asset rating	Asset rating	Asset/Operational rating	Asset rating
Country	Malta	Poland	Slovenia	Spain	UK
HVAC schedules	Default (based on zone activity type)	Assessor	Default (based on zone activity type)	Default (based on building type)	Default (based on zone activity type)
HVAC specification	Default values available	Default values available	Default values available	Actual values	Default values available
Lighting and equipment schedules	Default values	Default values or assessor	Default values	Default values	Default values
Occupancy schedules	Default values (mandatory)	Assessor	Default values (non-mandatory) or assessor	Default values (non-mandatory) or assessor	Default values (mandatory)
Construction thermal parameters	Database available/ inference based	Database available but outdated	Database available	Database available/ inference based	Database available/ inference based
Building envelope U-values	Database available (non-residential only)	Database available	Database available	Database available	Database available
Ventilation rates	Database available	Database available	Database available	Database available	Database available
Infiltration rate	Default values available	Default values available	Default values available	Default values available	Default values available (not for new buildings)
Temperature setpoints	Depends on use type/activity level/control/ different for heating and cooling season	Depends on use type/activity level/control/ different for heating and cooling season	Depends on use type/activity level/control/ different for heating and cooling season	Default values/different for heating and cooling season	Depends on use type/activity level/control/ different for heating and cooling season
Basic education	Engineers/Architects	Engineers	University degree in technical subject + 2 years' experience	Engineers/Architects/Professional with technical vocational training	Diverse background
Asset/operational rating	Asset rating	Asset/Operational rating	Asset/Operational rating	Asset rating	Asset rating

Comparison of inputs for partner countries methodologies

Figure 1. Comparison of inputs for partner countries methodologies

2.2 D3.2 (Performance gap causation) results

D3.2 *Performance gap causation* examines how the energy consumption of 65 tested buildings in nine different European countries—all of which have Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)—compares with the actual, measured energy consumption of those same buildings. Every single building is modelled using the regional EPC approach and contrasted with its metered energy use; when necessary, the EPC output is translated into a parameter that permits this comparison. The study highlights the difficulties in evaluating various approaches using various frameworks and metrics, especially when doing so across small samples of buildings.

It is evident from comparing the EPC certificates of various partner nations (Table 2) that various measures are employed when presenting the outcomes of EPC calculations. Certain nations solely offer data on primary energy consumption and carbon emissions, but others offer more comprehensive details, such as total final energy consumption, carbon emissions, and consumption numbers for different building services like lighting, heating, and cooling.

Table 2 shows that most nations provide final energy figures on their EPCs. However, the annual CO₂ emissions value is the only thing included in non-residential EPCs in England and Wales, the primary energy consumption is the only thing included in EPC certificates in Scotland, and the CO₂ emissions and primary energy consumption are the only things included in EPCs in Malta.

Table 2. Metrics provided in each country's EPC

Metrics provided in each country's EPC										
Country		Total CO ₂ emissions	Total primary energy	Total final energy	Final energy for heating	Final energy for hot water	Final energy for cooling	Final energy for lighting	Final energy for ventilation	Auxiliary electricity
Austria	Residential	X	X	X	X	X				
	Non-residential	X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Bulgaria		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Croatia		X	X	X	X		X			
Denmark					X					X
Greece		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Malta		X	X							

Poland		X	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Slovenia		X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Spain		X	X		X	X	X	X		
UK	Residential (Scotland)		X							
	Non-residential (Scotland)	X	X	X						
	Residential (Rest of the UK)				X	X				
	Non-residential (Rest of the UK)	X								

Other:

- Austria (non-residential) – humidification
- Greece – total final and primary energy disaggregated by fuel type
- Spain – primary energy consumption and CO₂ emissions for heating
- UK (residential) – annual cost rating

Metrics provided in each country's EPC

Figure 2. Metrics provided in each country's EPC.

Although most of the countries under study have EPCs that include total CO₂ emissions, total primary energy, total final energy, final energy for lighting, heating, hot water, cooling, and ventilation, the inclusion of auxiliary electricity and final energy for ventilation varies. Furthermore, there are other parameters including humidification, annual cost rating, fuel type disaggregation, and on-site renewable energy that are not often included in EPCs.

2.3 D2.5 (Cross testing data from existing EPCs) results

D2.5 gathers information from the first round of crossCert testing, including data and outcomes, as well as a first analysis of the collected data. One of the main obstacles in the first phase of cross-testing has been comprehending the EPC procedures of other nations. Except for the UK for non-residential buildings, where a dynamic model is used to provide results with temporal resolutions of, say, one hour, and Bulgaria, where a static model calibrated with actual energy consumption data is used, the majority of EPC methodologies are based on static models and provide results with an annual resolution.

Even yet, while most countries employ the same kind of model, each country has its own set of specialised procedures, levels of information necessary in the input data, and assumptions that are taken into account.

Indicators and Scales

The crossCert countries' EPC scales and indicators are summarised in Table 3. It displays a wide range of scales and metrics. Throughout Europe, the most prevalent indicators provided by EPC techniques are primary energy usage and CO₂ emissions. For building owners, these indications might not have the greatest significance, nonetheless.

In September 2021, Denmark introduced an easier-to-use format for the EPC report. The indicators for Denmark differ somewhat from those reported in other nations as a result. The building's power use and thermal energy consumption (from all sources) are the metrics that Danish EPCs provide. The building owner may be more familiar with these indicators. Additionally, there are distinct categories on the Danish EPC scale for zero-energy and passive dwellings. Additionally, the UK EPC offers other indicators. The energy cost and emissions are the foundation of the UK metrics. In addition, the UK EPC provides building owners with a comparison between the energy performance of their building and the national average for all buildings in the nation.

Table 3 presents metrics and scales that demonstrate the absence of European Union-wide standardisation of EPCs. Comparing between countries is challenging due to the wide range of measurements.

Table 3. Metrics provided in each country's EPC -updated with indicators and scales of EPCs in the crossCert countries (2024).

Metrics provided in each country's EPC (D3.2) updated with Indicators and scales of EPCs in the crossCert countries (D2.5)									
Country		Total CO ₂ emissions	Total primary energy	Total final energy	Final energy for heating	Final energy for hot water	Final energy for cooling	Final energy for lighting	Final energy for ventilation
Austria	Residential	Reference CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) A++ to G	Reference primary energy demand (kWh/m ² /year) A++ to G	X	Reference heating demand (kWh/m ² /year) A++ to G	X			
	Non-residential	Reference CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) A++ to G	Reference primary energy demand (kWh/m ² /year) A++ to G	X	Reference heating demand (kWh/m ² /year) A++ to G	X	X	X	
Bulgaria		X	Primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) A to G	X	X	X	X	X	X
Croatia		CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) No scale	Primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) A+, A, B, C, D, E, F, G	Delivered energy (kWh/m ² /year) No scale	Thermal energy for heating (kWh/m ² /year) A+, A, B, C, D, E, F, G		X	X	

Denmark					Heat energy consumption (kWh/year) from natural gas, electricity, district heating or other sources. A2020+ (passive energy houses), A2020 (zero energy buildings), A2015 (low energy buildings), A2010 (standard- low energy buildings), B, C, D, E, F, G				
Greece		CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) No scale	Ratio of primary energy consumption in the existing building with respect to the primary energy consumption in the reference building A+, A, B+, B, C, D, E, F, G Breakdown of primary energy consumption per use	X	X	X	X	X	
Malta		CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) A to G for non-residential buildings	X	Energy use (kWh/m ² /year) A to G for non-residential buildings					
Poland		CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) No scale	Primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) Graphic representation (no scale)	Energy demand (kWh/m ² /year) No scale	X	X	X	X	

Slovenia		CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) Graphic representation (no scale)	Primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) Graphic representation (no scale)	Energy for the building operation (kWh/m ² /year) Graphic representation (no scale)	Thermal energy for heating (kWh/m ² /year) A1, A2, B1, B2, C, D, E, F, G	X	X	X	X
Spain		CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) A to G	Non-renewable primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) A to G		Heating demand (kWh/m ² /year) A to G	X	Heating demand (kWh/m ² /year) A to G	X	
UK	Residential (Scotland)	Environmental impact rating (emissions metric) - Residential buildings A to G	Primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) No scale						
	Non-residential (Scotland)	CO ₂ emissions (kg/m ² /year) - Non-residential buildings No scale	Primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) No scale	Energy use (kWh/m ² /year) - Non-residential buildings No scale					
Country		Electricity	Auxiliary electricity	Humidification	Fuel type disaggregation	Energy efficiency factor	Renewable energy	nZEB	Annual cost rating
Austria	Residential					Overall energy efficiency factor (kWh/m ² /year) A++ to G			
	Non-residential			X		Overall energy efficiency factor (kWh/m ² /year) A++ to G			

Bulgaria			X						
Croatia									
Denmark		Electricity consumption (kWh/year) for building operation Electricity consumption (kWh/year) for other uses	X						
Greece					X				
Malta									
Poland									
Slovenia			X						
Spain									
UK	Residential (Scotland)					Energy efficiency rating (energy cost metric) – Residential buildings A to G			X
	Non-residential (Scotland)					Building energy performance rating – Non-residential buildings A+, A, B, C, D, E, F, G			

Recommendations for increased building energy efficiency

The majority of EPCs have a part with suggestions on how to raise the building's energy efficiency. The way in which certificates introduce these suggestions in the nations taking part in the cross-testing activities is explained in Table 4 and Figure 3. The following conclusions could be drawn from the examination of the process and the nature of these recommendations:

- In the EPC reports, the building's energy categorisation usually takes precedence over the recommendations. Frequently included as a required but supporting component at the conclusion of certificate reports are recommendations.
- No particular standards or guidelines, like the biggest emission reduction or shorter payback periods, are used to choose or rank the recommendations. Certain instances imply vague or nonspecific criteria. This is not like determining the energy class, where standardised calculations and assumptions are used.
- The certifier's abilities are the primary determinant of the suggestions made. In order to make appropriate suggestions and convince building owners to install energy-saving measures in their facilities, the certifier's knowledge and expertise are crucial.

Table 4. Characteristics of recommendations in the EPCs methodologies participating in the cross testing (2024).

Characteristics of recommendations in the EPCs methodologies participating in the cross testing					
Country	Mandatory, primary role in the EPC	Mandatory, secondary role in the EPC	Not mandatory, secondary role in the EPC	Tailored, depending on the issuer	Additional criteria
Austria		Included as free text in the technical annex of the EPC or the EPC program is used to define measures and calculate effects.		EPC issuer suggests suitable measures.	
Bulgaria		Described in the last page of the EPC (new label after the implementation of energy efficiency measures appear in the first page).		EPC issuer suggests suitable measures,	Also linked to more general recommendations (repair and maintenance).
Croatia		Described in the third page of the EPC.		EPC issuer suggests suitable measures.	Measures should be technically feasible.
Denmark	Highlighted and summarised on the first two pages of the EPC.			The EPC provides a list of measures tailored to the EPC results.	
Greece		Included in the last page of the EPC.		EPC issuer to include at least one recommendation with a list of possible measures.	Energy performance class is below "I" (C).
Malta		EPC includes reference values (a list with potential interventions) and is accompanied by a recommendation report.		Recommendation report is produced separately from the EPC.	

Poland			No, if measures are not technically feasible. EPC issuers can input comments and measures by hand. Filling recommendations is up to the auditor; EPCs have a blank space the auditor can use.	EPC issuer suggests suitable measures.	Measures should be technically feasible.
Slovenia		Included in the EPC.		EPC issuer suggests suitable measures.	
Spain		Included in the last pages of the EPC report (Annex III)		EPC issuer suggests suitable measures.	
UK	Reported on the first page of the EPC, furthermore, a recommendation report is produced separately from the EPC.			Recommendation report is produced separately from the EPC.	Measures ordered according to payback time.

Country	Calculation in Software	Default calculation inputs	Default list	Energy indicators	Environmental indicators	Economic indicators	New label
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Austria	EPC issuer creates a new building (refurbishment variant) as a copy of the existing building, to estimate the impact of the energy efficiency measures and obtain the energy, environmental and economic indicators as well as the new label of the building.			Energy savings	CO ₂ emissions	Cost savings, investment	New label
Bulgaria	The software used for the elaboration of the EPC is also valid to estimate the impact of energy efficiency measures.			Energy savings	CO ₂ emissions	Investment, payback	New label
Croatia	The optimal set of measured parameters is quantified by entering the same building in the software as a new building with all parameters such as new building envelope, new thermomechanical systems, and renewable energy systems. Measures are manually calculated in the energy audit report.			Energy savings	CO ₂ emissions	Investment, payback	New label
Denmark	The EPC protocol/software provide the modified performance results/indicators if the measure is applied (new energy consumption, new label, investment costs, payback period).			Energy savings	CO ₂ emissions	Cost savings, investment, payback	New label
Greece	The EPC software provides the modified performance results/indicators if the measures are applied (new energy consumption, new CO ₂ emissions, and new energy rating, investment costs, payback period).				CO ₂ emissions	Cost savings, investment	New label
Malta	The EPC software provides the modified performance results if the measures are applied.		For non-residential buildings	Energy savings	CO ₂ emissions	Investment, payback	New label

Poland	The EPC software does not provide (automatically) the modified performance results/indicators if the measures proposed by the auditor were implemented.			Depending on the EPC issuer.	Depending on the EPC issuer.	Depending on the EPC issuer.	Depending on the EPC issuer.
Slovenia	The EPC software provides a list of recommendations that EPC issuers could select according to their knowledge, experience, and results of the EPC calculations. The comparison of existing buildings to refurbished ones is not possible.			Depending on the EPC issuer.	Depending on the EPC issuer.	Depending on the EPC issuer.	Depending on the EPC issuer.
Spain	The software used for the elaboration of the EPC is also valid to estimate the impact of energy efficiency measures.			Energy savings, demand reduction in each energy consumption category	CO ₂ emissions		New label
UK	EPCs are quite standardised and replicable, drawing recommendations from a set list of options that, although tailored for a particular building, are quite recognisable across different EPCs.			Energy savings		Cost savings, investment	New label

Characteristics of recommendations in the EPCs methodologies participating in the cross testing

Figure 3. Characteristics of recommendations in the EPCs methodologies participating in the cross testing

Establishing a building's energy classification and offering advice to the building owner on how to increase the facility's energy efficiency are the two primary duties of an energy performance certificate (EPC). One of the findings from the cross-testing process is that, at the moment, energy certification is primarily concerned with identifying the building's energy class, with the EPC recommendations being viewed as a supporting element. The UK and Denmark are the sole exceptions, as the recommendations are emphasised in the new structure for energy certificates.

In order to compare the energy performance of buildings that share the same premises, the calculating methodology must be standardised. But in order to offer effective suggestions for enhancing energy efficiency, a more building-specific model is required, one that takes into account aspects like occupancy and actual user behaviour—both of which have a significant impact on the building's energy use. The building owner's involvement may rise with the certificate's personalisation. More personalisation, however, suggests a higher certificate price. For the next generation of EPCs, standardisation and an appropriate level of personalisation are challenges.

3 Output data

3.1 D3.3 (Analysis of new scales and KPIs) results

An overview of the most recent developments in scales and key performance indicators (KPIs) intended to improve the accuracy and applicability of energy performance evaluations may be found in the study on the Analysis of New Scales and KPIs for Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs). In addition to analysing the KPIs utilised in other Horizon 2020 projects, the paper looks at the numerous KPIs based on the criteria of smartness, human-centric indicator, energy performance, financial parameters, and climate change.

KPIs are separated into five categories, each of which has been given a unique colour:

- Smartness (yellow)
- Human-Centric (blue)
- Energy performance (green)
- Financial (pink)
- Climate change (red)

This assessment of KPIs from several European projects makes it easier to compare various perspectives on the existence of buildings. Notably, factors related to energy performance and intelligence are typically the main foci of these projects. The project's orientation in this trajectory can be explained by the fact that smartness, as measured by the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), is emerging as a relatively new notion inside European legislation. Because energy performance indicators are widely used in all of the nation's processes, they are also preferred in European projects.

Additionally, the study explores the application of KPIs in partner countries, including Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Greece, Malta, Poland, Slovenia, Spain, and the UK (Scotland) (Table 5). The significance of energy performance throughout a building's lifecycle is emphasised by the fact that all partner countries include Energy Performance indicators into national EPC frameworks. The report's recommendation for suitable output measurements and KPIs that can satisfy the new EPC requirements comes to a close.

With 44 KPIs in total on the first page of the EPC in each country, the "energy performance" category's indicators are now the most widely used ones. The indicators from the "climate change" category, which are all connected to CO₂ emissions, are the second most popular category. Financial KPIs ranked third in popularity, with a precise count of eight. The absence of "human-centric" and "smartness" indicators from the home page may be the result of new indicators being added to these categories.

It is evident that the vast majority of the KPIs listed on the front page of the EPC fall under the category of "Energy Performance," since the Energy Performance Certificate serves as a document that calculates the quantity of energy needed to meet the energy needs associated with the use of a building or part of a building. The indications pertaining to a building's CO₂ emissions serve as a clear example of the goal, which is to encourage energy-efficient construction and increase public knowledge of the possibility for energy savings in buildings.

It is crucial to think about whether the abundance of KPIs benefits the building owner/user or assessors and other officials who can access the EPC for statistical and technical reasons, or if they are solely for the benefit of these parties. The EPC examples from UK (Scotland) and Denmark demonstrate a human-centred approach, with the majority of the page devoted to describing the data. This makes the EPC easier to read and is more likely to result in the suggested improvements being implemented in

practice. The legend or guidance on how to understand the values should be included in EPCs, and the most significant data should be indicated either graphically or textually (e.g., by incorporating infographics).

Table 5. Metrics provided in each country's EPC -updated with indicators and scales of EPCs in the crossCert countries and new KPIs (2024). Highlighted (in bold) KPIs with which scales are developed in the certificates.

Metrics provided in each country's EPC (D3.2) updated with indicators and scales of EPCs in the crossCert countries (D2.5) and new KPIs (D3.3)									
Country		Total CO ₂ emissions	Total primary energy	Total final energy	Final energy for heating	Final energy for hot water	Final energy for cooling	Final energy for lighting	Final energy for ventilation
Austria	Residential	Total equivalent carbon dioxide emissions (greenhouse gases) (CO₂eq)	Primary energy demand (PEB)	End energy demand (EEB)	Reference heat energy demand (HWBRef) Heating energy demand (HEB)	Hot water heating demand (WWWB)			
	Non-residential	Total equivalent carbon dioxide emissions (greenhouse gases) (CO₂eq)	Primary energy demand (PEB)	End energy demand (EEB)	Reference heat energy demand (HWBRef) Heating energy demand (HEB)	Hot water heating demand (WWWB)	Cooling energy demand (KEB)	X	
Bulgaria		Generated CO ₂ emissions at normalised condition [tCO ₂ /year] Generated CO ₂ emissions after energy saving measures [tCO ₂ /year]	Primary energy – total [kWh/m², kWh/year] Primary non-renewable energy [kWh/m ² , kWh/year] Primary renewable energy [kWh/m ² , kWh/year] Share of the primary renewable energy at normalised condition [%] Share of the primary renewable energy after energy saving measures [%]	Energy consumption in normalised state [MWh /year] Distribution of annual energy consumption [%]	X	X	X	X	X

Croatia		Specific annual CO ₂ emission [kg/(m ² year)]	Specific annual primary energy (E _{prim}) [kWh/(m ² year)]	Specific annual delivered energy (Edel) [kWh/ (m ² year)]	Specific annual heat energy requirements for heating (QH, nd) [kWh/(m ² year)]		X	X	
Denmark		Total CO ₂ emissions [ton]		Energy consumption of the building Energy consumption of the building after energy saving measures	Current energy class				
Greece		Estimated annual CO ₂ emissions [kg / m ²] Actual annual CO ₂ emissions [kg / m ²]	Breakdown of primary energy consumption per use Estimated annual primary energy consumption: Reference building [kWh/m ²] and Inspected building [kWh/m ²] Total annual primary energy consumption [kWh/m ²]	Actual annual consumption of the inspected building	Heating (fuel) [kWh/m ²]	X	X	X	
Malta		Carbon dioxide emissions [kg/(m ² year)]	x	Energy use [kWh/(m ² year)]					

Poland		Specific CO ₂ emissions (ECO ₂) [t CO ₂ /(m ² year)]	Primary energy consumption (kWh/m ² /year) Graphic representation (no scale) Index of annual demand for non-renewable primary energy (EP) [kWh/(m ² year)]	Index of annual useful energy demand (EU) [kWh/(m ² year)] Index of annual final energy demand (EK) [kWh/(m ² year)] Share of renewable energy sources in annual final energy demand (Uoze) [%].	X	X	X	X	
Slovenia		CO ₂ emission [kg/(m ² year)]	Primary energy [kWh/(m ² year)]	Delivered energy for building operation [kWh/(m ² year)]	Energy demand for heating A1-G [kWh/(m ² year)]	X	X	X	X
Spain		Carbon dioxide emissions [kgCO ₂ e/(m ² year)]	Non-renewable primary energy consumption [kWh/(m ² year)]		Heating demand (kWh/m ² /year) [A to G]	X	Cooling demand (kWh/m ² /year) [A to G]	X	
UK	Residential (Scotland)	Environmental impact (CO ₂) Rating (current - potential) [A-G]	Primary Energy Indicator [kWh/(m ² year)]						
	Non-residential (Scotland)	CO ₂ emissions [(kg/m ² /year)] Non-residential buildings No scale	Primary Energy Indicator [kWh/(m ² year)]	Energy use [(kWh/m ² /year)] Non-residential buildings No scale					

Country		Electricity	Auxiliary electricity	Humidification	Fuel type disaggregation	Energy efficiency factor	Renewable energy	nZEB	Annual cost rating	Other cost parameters
Austria	Residential	Household electricity demand (HHSB)				Total energy efficiency factor (fGEE)				
	Non-residential	Operating electricity demand (BSB)		X		Total energy efficiency factor (fGEE)				
Bulgaria			X				Exported renewable energy [kWh/year] Share of renewable energy demand for heating, cooling, ventilation, DHW and lighting [%]			
Croatia								nZEB rating, if the energy performance of the building (Eprim) meets the requirements		

Denmark		Electricity consumption (kWh/year) for building operation Electricity consumption (kWh/year) for other uses	X						How much the owner overpays for energy per year (if applicable)	Energy consultant recommendations with listed annual money savings and investment price District heating [kr.] Electricity for other [kr.] Total energy cost [kr.]
Greece		Electricity [kWh/m ²]			X	Current energy class Energy class after energy saving measures				
Malta										
Poland										
Slovenia			X							
Spain										
UK	Residential (Scotland)					Energy Efficiency Rating (current - potential) [A-G]			Estimated energy costs for a house for 3 years [£]	Savings over 3 years [£] Actions to take to save money and make house more efficient [£]
	Non-residential (Scotland)					Building energy performance rating - Non-residential buildings [A+, A, B, C, D, E, F, G]				

3.2 D2.6 (Cross testing of first generation of new EPCs) results

The first wave of new EPC approach proposals that have been made available since the project's inception are detailed in the report D2.6. These proposals mostly relate to the techniques and procedures created for EU2020 projects U-CERT, QualDeEPC, and X-tendo.

Proposals were examined for enhanced EPC features across all projects that offer such a feature in order to facilitate more effective and relevant testing. The tested features, chosen from each of the three projects, are:

1. **EPC certificate reports**
2. **Complete online tools for energy performance assessment**
3. **Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI)**
4. **Comfort Asset Rating Procedure (CARP)**
5. **Renovation recommendations for improved energy efficiency**
6. **Regular training**
7. **EPCs in advertising and sales**

3.2.1 EPC report format and content

An outline of the main conclusions and recommendations from the cross-validation process about the structure and contents of the EPC report, along with the recommendations from QualDeEPC and U-CERT, is given below:

- It is preferable to issue **a single EPC report** rather than two, one for the assessor and one for the end user.
- **Technical annexes should come after a two- to three-page synopsis that highlights the most crucial information for the end user in this single report.**
- **Including data on energy consumption in the EPC report** to guarantee accurate and representative measurements of energy consumption over extended periods of time.
- **Using infographics together with a text description and standardised scaling, like colours and characters, as is presently done for building energy efficiency, to incorporate new indicators like Thermal Score or SRI into the EPC.**
- **Providing end users with options for further action, such as contacting financial organisations, energy specialists, or one-stop shops upon receiving the certificate.**
- Evaluating the technological systems and building envelope, as well as putting in place a **traffic light system** for evaluating each component.
- **The way the EPC data and outcomes are presented visually, with infographics being used extensively.**
- The provision of online access to EPCs, which might provide users with more details and definitions of terms and concepts used in the certificate, as well as examples of best practices and advice on how to put the recommendations in the certificate into effect.

3.2.2 Online tool for energy performance assessment

An outline of the main conclusions and recommendations from the cross-testing process for the online energy performance assessment tool created as part of the QualDeEPC project is given below:

- User-friendly tool that requires little to no knowledge of building energy performance.
- Extremely useful tool for teaching and bringing to light deep energy renovations in buildings for end users.

- The availability of these tools on public portals or one-stop shop websites for energy renovations in buildings;
- The Danish Energy Agency has created a thorough portal at <https://sparenergi.dk/> that gives building owners access to diverse tools and information to help them with house renovations. This portal is a great illustration of a resource that informs and engages building owners regarding improvements.

3.2.3 Smart Readiness Indicator

An outline of the main conclusions and recommendations from the cross-testing exercise concerning X-tendo's Smart Readiness Indicator (Abbreviated Method) is given below:

- The use of SRI in EPCs: EPC issuers might be able to conduct SRI assessments using the shortened technique without the need for further training. It is advised that some sort of training be offered to help with the SRI assessment procedure.
- Public relations efforts, the display of successful case studies, incentives, the establishment of a clear connection between SRI and building management systems, and the streamlining of the SRI assessment procedure.
- The advantages of enhancing the building's sustainability should be emphasised, with a focus on the effects on the environment, finances, and energy.
- Coordination of building performance evaluation metrics and tools, such as Building Renovation Passports (BRP), Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), Energy Performance Certificates (EPC), Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI), HVAC (heating, ventilation, and air conditioning) inspections, and Indoor Environmental Quality (IEQ), offers several advantages, including a comprehensive assessment for the building owner that makes the decision-making process for building renovations easier.

3.2.4 Comfort Asset Rating Procedure (CARP)

An outline of the main conclusions and recommendations from the cross-testing process concerning X-tendo's Comfort Asset Rating Procedure (CARP) is given below:

- Buildings with inadequate façade insulation may receive high ratings for "acoustic comfort," "visual comfort," and "indoor air quality." - These results could lead to misunderstandings among end users and damage the comfort indicator's reliability.
- The approach is not modified to take certain nations' comfort levels into account.
- When assessing building comfort, thermal comfort is far more important than auditory or visual comfort.
- Comfort is very individualised and subjective to the user.
- User behaviour also affects the comfort score (mostly in terms of interior air quality and thermal comfort), in addition to the building's features. For more realistic comfort assessments, the technique should take this user behaviour influence into account.
- Enhancing the tool's user-friendliness and usability by adding default values or more information explaining each parameter individually.
- The incorporation of national EPC procedures with the CARP approach would increase energy efficiency of the building as comfort indicators are a major driver of building renovation activity. However, **financial considerations like necessary investments or cost savings continue to be the main determining factors.**
- Providing end users access to information about the variables that have a major impact on comfort, along with practical suggestions for enhancing it; including concise explanations of the connections between the comfort metrics and the energy renovation measures suggested by

EPCs; and determining the updated comfort scores following the implementation of energy renovation measures.

3.2.5 Renovation recommendations for improved energy efficiency

The following provides an overview of the primary findings and suggestions from the cross-testing exercise in relation to the proposals of QualDeEPC and X-tendo to enhance the renovation recommendations provided in EPCs.

- The tool developed by X-tendo has been identified as a valuable resource for generating EPC recommendations.
- The tool developed by QualDeEPC has been widely recognised for its usefulness as a guide for the implementation of deep energy recommendations in energy certificates.
- The improvement in performance of buildings that adopt the recommendations provided by the QualDeEPC tool conforms to the standards of deep energy renovation in most crossCert countries.
- The proposal of X-tendo for linking EPC recommendations to building-stock targets in long-term national renovation plans has received positive feedback from cross testers.
- The payback periods for most buildings where deep energy renovations have been tested, particularly those with higher initial energy rating (B, C, D), are significantly longer. As a result, deep energy renovation measures are often not cost effective.
- Recommendations about technical systems generally require lower investments and have shorter payback periods than envelope-related measures - may lead users to prioritise the renewal of technical systems over envelope elements.
- **The incorporation of financial options into EPCs; the implementation of building renovation passports;** and the provision of precise information to the building owner regarding the long-term benefits of deep energy renovations such as enhanced comfort indicators, property value, health, and sustainability. The ageing of the building also may serve as a fundamental argument to persuade building owners to implement renovations.
- In Denmark, there are specific guidelines for providing renovation recommendations. These guidelines are outlined in the mandatory requirements of the Handbook for Energy Consultants and dictate the following provisions:
 - a. All feasible measures should be included.
 - b. Improvements to all uninsulated elements should be suggested.
 - c. Proposals for use of renewables (e.g. heat pump systems and solar energy) or district heating should be suggested where applicable.
 - d. Other measures can be included based on the judgement of the assessor.
 - e. Building constraints should be considered, such as building preservation.
- In some countries, such as Austria, Denmark, the UK, Spain, and Greece, the certification software supports issuing EPC recommendations. This includes the development and evaluation of renovation options, default recommendations adapted to the building, or predefined energy efficiency measures.
- Integrated databases in certification software offer valuable support to EPC issuers. In Denmark, Austria, and Spain, **standard data for costs, lifetime, and energy prices are integrated into certification software.**
- Denmark's financial sector involvement in supporting the implementation of energy renovation measures represents a success story and a model.

3.3 D5.1 (Report on existing attitudes, expectations and needs) results

D5.1 provides a fresh perspective on understanding energy performance certificates (EPCs) from a people-centred perspective. In summary, the positive things of existing EPCs with regard to their design are:

- that they provide data and information regarding energy performance and possible renovation measures for the building,
- that they provide some visualised reference regarding the building's energy performance, and again,
- that such a tool exists in the first place.

Some of the key negative aspects they highlight are

- lack of context and explanations,
- high density of data and information,
- poor visual presentation of information, and
- absence of certain information (e.g. cost-related info, further sources of information, possibility for monitoring energy use).

It therefore seems that EPC schemes, at least in some countries, have been created by experts for experts, and not for the general population, or at least not with the understanding of what (non-expert) users of EPCs might need to understand in order to use them meaningfully. Bančič et al. pointed out, that existing EPCs are:

- Complex and difficult to understand for general users (terminology, incomprehensive measuring units used, no clear relation between individual pieces of data and information, etc.).
- Lack clear references to long-term benefits of performance improvement and further sources of information.
- Often do not relate to the actual building, which is subject to the assessment, etc.

Unsurprisingly, this led Bančič et al. to call for more:

- guidance on how to read, understand and use EPCs,
- visual representation of information, and
- more contextualisation with relatable information for general users (financial references, comparisons to buildings they already know, etc.).

With reference to the conceptualisation of EPC users as outlined above, general users can be understood as people who possess a lesser extent of relevant EPC-related knowledge than those categorised as expert users. These profiles would typically require some form of guidance and support. Alternatively (or in addition), these profiles need to have a significant level of motivation and cognitive capacity to gather and/or interpret the relevant EPC-related information, all of which enables them to generate the knowledge, confidence and motivation required to make meaningful use of EPCs.

In the context of T5.1, we compiled the following working version of the list of expert EPC user profiles:

- Existing homeowners
- Prospective homeowners
- New-build investors
- Household tenants
- Business tenants
- Building users

In general, recommendations are as follows:

- **Improve the existing design of EPC products and services** - relates to provision of clear information, tailored to the knowledge profile of the user:
 - **Obligatory use of a distinct energy efficiency rating scale.**
 - **Dual energy rating**
 - **Provide a key/legend or a guide on how to read, understand, and use the EPCs** - include optional key or orientation manual for a comprehensive use of EPCs (to explain the elements of EPCs; to explain the specific language and concepts used, including units and suggested measures; to explain how individual elements of the EPC relate to each other etc.).
 - **Enhance visual representation** - include graphs, infographics, colour-segmentation of the document etc.
- **Improve elements of EPC user experience** - prioritise certain information depending on specific user profiles, particularly with the order in which elements are presented in the EPCs. Reducing the quantity and density of information whenever possible is an aspect that relates to the point on visual representation, which would be made possible especially (but not exclusively!) with digitalisation of EPCs that would enable hiding certain elements of EPCs (meta information) deemed less important for specific user profiles. Digitalisation would also enable a more interactive interface (gamification) to enhance the user experience.
- **Relate energy performance ratings with aspects that specific users find meaningful** - provide the kind of information that is most meaningful and relevant.
 - **Highlight correlation between energy efficiency and comfort, health, safety, aesthetics and other relevant qualitative aspects.**
 - **Provide forecasts of potential financial benefits.**
 - **Demonstrate the qualitative value created by building renovation/retrofitting for specific target groups (e.g. a household).**
 - **Demonstrate qualitative value building renovation/retrofitting creates beyond your target group – for the local community, professional community, society, etc.**
- **Provide relevant information at appropriate time, depending on the specific user profile**
 - **Enable EPCs with various levels of complexity for different user profiles.**
- **Make the EPC concept future-proof.** Revised reports suggest that EPC schemes should be designed as a framework that can be changed according to the seemingly inevitable and ever-faster technological and scientific advancements and innovations, which are certainly also going to have an impact on the construction sector.
 - **Enable a flexible rating scale.**
 - **Digitalise EPCs**
- **Convert EPCs into a “building passport”** - evolve towards more comprehensive, dynamic tools accompanying a building over its lifetime.

3.4 D5.2 (Survey and workshop results of EPC end-users) results

The activity itself asked participants to consider six different features of EPCs (three relating to the information provided, three to the aesthetics/presentation of EPCs) and suggest a preference for each feature; that is, a delivery of that feature that would directly benefit their own use of EPCs. These features were:

- A. **Choice of outputs:** Ranging from traditional EPC ratings to outputs accommodating new metrics
- A. **Improvement recommendations:** The inclusion of recommendations within or without a single EPC document, and the extent of standardisation of text used to describe those measures
- A. **Basis of output data:** The use of modelled or measured estimates of energy use (or a combination)
- A. **General format:** Online/interactive access or traditional paper/e-copies of the certificate (or a combination)
- A. **Output format (primary form of information):** The use of graphical and/or tabular information to communicate key outputs
- A. **Overall length of document(s):** Single page, multi-page, or multi-document

Feedback from participants

The results of the Group 1 (**Building users and architects**) discussion are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Group 1 preferences for EPC features

Category/Feature	Options				
	1	2	3	4	
Information	A. Choice of outputs	EPC rating and related info (i.e. as required by EPBD)	EPC rating + information available from current assessment	EPC rating + new metrics requiring extra data collection from new assessment	
	B. Improvement recommendations	Part of document in summarised/standardised form	Part of document, specific to the property (e.g. created by assessor)	Not Part of main document and summarised/standardised elsewhere	Not part of main document, specific to the property (e.g. created by assessor)
	C. Basis of output data	Only modelled estimates	Only measured estimates	Combination	
Aesthetics	D. General format	Online, interactive interface	Paper/PDF	Combination	
	E. Output format (primary form of information)	Graphical	Tabular	Textual	Combination
	F. Overall length of document(s)	1 page	Multiple page, single document	Multiple documents	

The results of the Group 3 (**Policy related**) discussion are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Group 3 preferences for EPC features

Information	A. Choice of outputs	EPC rating and related info (i.e. as required by EPBD)	EPC rating + information available from current assessment	EPC rating + new metrics requiring extra data collection from new assessment	
	B. Improvement recommendations	Part of document in summarised/standardised form	Part of document, specific to the property (e.g. created by assessor)	Not Part of main document and summarised/standardised elsewhere	Not part of main document, specific to the property (e.g. created by assessor)
	C. Basis of output data	Only modelled estimates	Only measured estimates	Combination	
Aesthetics	D. General format	Online, interactive interface	Paper/PDF	Combination	
	E. Output format (primary form of information)	Graphical	Tabular	Textual	Combination
	F. Overall length of document(s)	1 page	Multiple page, single document	Multiple documents	

Nonetheless, significant agreement was discovered for some of the categories under discussion, even though the individuals' backgrounds differed. It was evident that there are widespread views for how an EPC should be presented among the groups. Participants were asked to imagine an ideal EPC, which they then defined as a multi-page document that uses several data presentation modes (text, tabular, and graphical) and expands on this beyond the conventional hard copy of the EPC by using internet resources. The EPC's inclusion in a collection of documents made the building user/architect group feel more at ease.

Regarding the information itself, there was greater variety throughout the groups. All groups were eager to maintain the standardised EPC outputs (ratings, etc.) as the primary source of information, maybe because they were familiar with the current EPC formats in their respective fields of work. Nevertheless, a few EPC assessors were more receptive to the incorporation of next-generation measures. This does show the legacy of established measurements, both in a good way (recognition across sectors) and a bad way (it is challenging to suggest additions to or adjustments to existing indicators).

A slightly divided group of EPC assessors preferred the current use of standardised recommendations, possibly due to the common use of this approach in current EPCs. However, both the policy and EPC assessor groups saw value in having improvement recommendations that were more specific to a property (rather than generalised for a typical property). The building user/architect group recommended that more thorough information about the recommendations be made available outside of the primary document, although they still thought that standardised information should be acknowledged in this respect.

3.5 Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council

In addition to implementing renovation requirements and upgrading the construction standard, the DIRECTIVE (EU) 2024/1275 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL strengthens the enabling framework and offers new or greater benefits to people in terms of financial help, information, and advice.

According to Article 19, Article 20, Annex V, and Annex VI on improved EPCs, EPCs are a crucial instrument for informing the public about a building's energy efficiency. The EPC framework is greatly enhanced by the Directive.

Member states must make sure that the "appropriate distribution of energy performance indicators" is maintained between the "B" and "F" classes and must **recalibrate the EPC classes using just the letters "A" through "G."** It is imperative for Member States to guarantee that the definition of class limits, or upper and lower thresholds, prevents the emergence of excessively tiny or big classes. This will guarantee a fair distribution of buildings among the classes, allowing Member States to promptly choose which buildings should be given priority for renovation projects.

Some EPC classes should be commonly used across Member States:

- 'G' class should cover the very-worst-performing buildings (defined at national level).
- 'A' class should correspond to ZEB.
- 'A+' class, if Member States decide to use it, should be defined at the national level as "building with a maximum threshold for energy demand which is at least 20% lower than the maximum threshold for ZEB, and which generates more renewable energy on-site annually than its total annual primary energy demand".

As of May 29, 2026, newly issued EPCs should be subject to the revised scale. One exception exists: Member states may delay the rescaling until December 31, 2029, if they rescaled their EPCs between January 1, 2019, and summer 2024 (the time the EPBD came into effect). However, rescaling is not the sole aspect of reforming EPCs. Although the Directive has made numerous improvements to the quality of its material, given the provisions on EPC implementation, the enhancement potential will not be fully realised.

EPCs shall communicate energy performance in a common way – i.e. with numeric indicators of both primary and final energy use in kWh/m²/year – and include, for comparison purposes, reference values (MEPS, NZEB, ZEB). The Directive also introduces **a common EPC template**, to be mandatorily used as of 29/05/2026. It specifies which elements the EPC should include, along three categories of indicators:

- (1) mandatory indicators on the front page specifically,
- (2) mandatory indicators overall, and
- (3) optional indicators.

The common EPC template is explained in ANNEX V:

Template for energy performance certificates (referred to in Article 19)

1. On its front page, the energy performance certificate shall display at least the following elements:

- (a) the energy performance class.
- (b) the calculated annual primary energy use in kWh/(m² y).
- (c) the calculated annual final energy use in kWh/(m² y).
- (d) renewable energy produced on-site in % of energy use.
- (e) operational greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO₂/(m² y)), and the value of the life-cycle GWP, if available.

The energy performance certificate shall also display the following elements:

- (a) the calculated annual primary and final energy consumption in kWh or MWh.
- (b) renewable energy production in kWh or MWh; main energy carrier and type of renewable energy source.
- (c) the calculated energy needs in kWh/(m² y).
- (d) a yes/no indication whether the building has a capacity to react to external signals and adjust the energy consumption.
- (e) a yes/no indication whether the heat distribution system inside the building is capable to work at low or more efficient temperature levels, where applicable.
- (f) the contact information of the relevant one-stop shop for renovation advice.

2. In addition, the energy performance certificate may include the following indicators:

- (a) energy use, peak load, size of generator or system, main energy carrier and main type of element for each of the uses: heating, cooling, domestic hot water, ventilation and in-built lighting.
- (b) the greenhouse gas emission class (if applicable).
- (c) information on carbon removals associated to the temporary storage of carbon in or on buildings.
- (d) a yes/no indication whether a renovation passport is available for the building.
- (e) the average U-value for the opaque elements of the building envelope.
- (f) the average U-value for the transparent elements of the building envelope.
- (g) type of most common transparent element (e.g. double-glazed window).
- (h) results of the analysis on overheating risk (if available).
- (i) the presence of fixed sensors that monitor the indoor environmental quality.
- (j) the presence of fixed controls that respond to the levels of indoor environmental quality.
- (k) number and type of recharging points for electric vehicles.
- (l) presence, type and size of energy storage systems.
- (m) expected remaining lifespan of the heating or air-conditioning systems and appliances, where applicable.
- (n) feasibility of adapting the heating system to operate at more efficient temperature settings.
- (o) feasibility of adapting the domestic hot-water system to operate at more efficient temperature settings.
- (p) feasibility of adapting the air-conditioning system to operate at more efficient temperature settings.
- (q) metered energy consumption.
- (r) whether there is a connection to a district heating and cooling network, and, if available, information about a potential connection to an efficient district heating and cooling system.
- (s) local primary energy factors and related carbon emission factors of the connected local district heating and cooling network.
- (t) operational fine particulate matter (PM 2.5) emissions.

The energy performance certificate may include the following links with other initiatives if these apply in the relevant Member State:

- (a) a yes/no indication whether a smart readiness assessment has been carried out for the building.
- (b) where available, the value of the smart readiness assessment.
- (c) a yes/no indication whether a Digital Building Logbook is available for the building.

The introduction of a template with additional indicators will enhance the comprehensiveness of information, which citizens can access regarding the building they own or occupy.

The Directive also **widens the scope of EPC recommendations**, which should increase their impact. Next to the energy performance improvements and steps to achieve them, recommendations must now also include more details on:

- The energy savings and operational GHG emissions reduction potential.
- The improvement of indoor environmental quality.
- Financial incentives and benefits.

- Available administrative and technical support.
- Possible alternatives for the replacement of the heating and cooling system.

Furthermore, if it is technically, financially, and functionally possible, the Directive Article 10 mandates the progressive deployment of solar energy installations on currently-existing public and non-residential buildings.

Lastly, the Directive (Annex VI) significantly expands and fortifies regulations related to EPC quality control, particularly those pertaining to the legitimacy and (public) accessibility to EPCs.

The Directive also introduces renovation passports in coordination with other tools within the renovation ecosystem, especially the EPC. **The renovation passport should build on the information included in the EPC and shall indicate the estimated EPC class to be achieved following completion of the steps outlined. Renovation passports can also be drawn up and issued jointly with EPCs – in these cases, the renovation passport shall replace the recommendations section of the EPC.** There are positive synergies between renovation passports and EPCs, avoiding overlaps and maximising the impacts of both tools. The introduction of renovation passports in the Directive also achieves a balance between a forward-looking (digital) approach and quality safeguards. **The renovation passport shall be issued in a digital format and shall be stored in or accessed via a digital building logbook (DBL) when one is available.** Quality and reliability in turn are ensured by the requirement that a renovation passport can only be issued by a qualified or certified expert following an on-site visit of the building.

The Directive introduces a separate Article on one-stop shops, giving them more prominence as key information and advisory tools for renovation. It also recognises the crucial role they play in supporting the delivery of other provisions, such as MEPS, and draws links between one-stop-shops and other tools, such as EPCs and renovation passports. These identified synergies should boost the use of one-stop-shops. **Both EPCs and renovation passports must contain, as a mandatory element, the contact information of relevant one-stop-shops (Annex V and Annex VIII). When an issued EPC is below class 'C', building owners shall be invited to receive renovation advice in a one-stop-shop.**

4 EPC translating tool

4.1 General description

The terms of reference list the requirements that **EPC translation tool** (i.e. energy certificate-based calculating online tool), must meet. The EPC translation tool is an interactive web application that makes use of data from energy certificates, by manually entering data contained in energy certificate. The most economical way to improve energy efficiency while still adhering to regulations (such the nZEB standard) will be automatically calculated by the tool and highlighted. The actions involved in the building renovation passport (BRP) will be clearly outlined using the data collected to produce an intuitive EPC format. The present regulations of each country specify what needs to be done to fulfil the criteria.

A prototype of the user-friendly format could be retrieved from both U-CERT and QualDeEPC new formats proposals for the EPC report ([U-CERT report](#), [QualDeEPC report](#)).

No matter what computer platform or location they are using, users should be able to use any standard web browser to access the tool. **Future modules or additions must be able to be added to the tool's structure.**

The EPC translating tool needs to include the following features:

Platform hierarchy: User accounts

- Using the system and logging out as a user.
- User accounts can be created by the administrator on demand.
- Interface for administrators:
 - Editing by users.
 - Establishing calculation parameters (current energy costs, unit costs for energy-saving measures, and other – such database entered by administrator in each country is needed for the calculation of recommendations).
 - Permit the administrator to save three variations of the aforementioned parameters, from which users will be able to choose the final option.

Buildings

- Entering a new building in two levels (simple and complex entry, import of buildings).
- Inspect the buildings.
- Exporting a database to Excel.
- The ability to update the status of buildings.

Energy efficiency measures

- Review of measures (proposed measures, accepted measures).
- Measures calculation (approx. 10 measures).

Analysis and results

- A table and graphical representation of the computation's findings showing which combination of RES and EnU measures will be most cost-effective for a given building to meet required criteria.
 - The user may select the combination of measures to be applied.
- The option to export data analysis results as an Excel, Word, or PDF report.
- The capability to select and arrange results according to various standards.

Support

4.2 User accounts

The building owner/user (Manager or Main Manager) receives a username and password from the administrator, which they can use to log into the application system. The administrator also chooses which objects are visible to which users; for instance, a user would only view buildings that he owns.

Application access or privilege levels:

- Admin editing, editing and reviewing – Administrator
- Editing and Reviewing – Main Manager
- Overview – Manager
- Blocked user

The parameters that are used to perform the calculations are controlled using the administrator interface. Permitting the alteration of those parameters is necessary. All users have access to this interface, but only the admin can edit the data (admin edit).

4.3 Buildings

With editing and admin editing options, a user may create a new building entry.

There are two levels to the entry:

1. Simple data entry

- The most basic data is entered,
- Suitable for buildings on which detailed information is not available,
- Other data that has not been entered shall be annulled with estimated values that have been integrated into the application.

2. Complex data entry

- Every necessary parameter for calculating the measures must be entered.
- When entering complex data, the first view shows estimated values, which are displayed in a distinct colour.

Tracking and recording any entry or modification of static input data necessitates keeping track of the entered values and the system user who typed or modified the designated value. This creates a historical record that needs to be archived following the deadline and maintained in the system for a minimum of ten years.

It should be possible for various documents in .doc, .jpeg, .xls, .pdf, .dwg, and related formats to be attached to each building. These documents should be saved online. Furthermore, each building should include related energy certificates and, if feasible, an energy audit report as a fundamental component of the description. As a result, each building's attachments are categorised as follows:

- Energy certificate.
- Energy audit report.
- Project documentation.
- Ownership and legality.
- Photo documentation.
- Other.

Comparison of buildings according to different categories (energy efficiency level, energy/CO₂ savings potential) should be enabled by setting up unified indicators defined in Table 3.

Buildings and the connections between them need to be clearly identified by assigning each object a unique identification. Every building ought to be visible on Google Maps (if the argument of data protection is resolved), and each one should have a link that may be clicked to bring up a pop-up window with tabular data on it.

Buildings can have several labels attached to them, allowing for result filtering. Only the user whose account created the label can see it; labels are assigned by the Administrator and the Master Manager.

The use of energy sources in accordance with specified circumstances is one of a building's fundamental characteristics. In the event that it is unknown, the EPC translation tool must perform an automatic calculation.

The repository must be configured so that previous documents and data are remembered when importing new ones. A basic and transparent form that provides answers to the questions of what, who, and when can be used to record a historical overview. Once you remove documents or data, the system truly erases them.

4.4 Recommendations

The energy efficiency measures listed below are calculated to determine the most cost-effective combination of measures:

- Thermal insulation of exterior walls.
- Thermal insulation of the roof (different variants of the roof).
- Replacement of exterior windows and doors.
- Installation of a new heating system:
 - Condensing gas boiler.
 - Pellet boiler.
 - Wood chips boiler.
 - Heat pump:
 - Air.
 - Earth.
 - Water.
 - Heating plant.
 - The solar thermal panels.
- Forced ventilation system with heat recovery.
- Cooling system.
- Replacement of interior lighting.
- Installation of solar thermal panels for hot water.
- Installation of photovoltaic panels.

4.5 Results

- An instrument that is user-friendly and accessible to non-experts,
- Outlining the most economical set of steps to do in order to meet the desired requirement,
- The ability to compare investment costs and energy savings while considering multiple alternative measure combinations,
- The possibility to prioritise the recommendations and define timeline (connection to BRPs),

- A database that makes it easier to enter building-related data and allows genuine values to be freely entered,
- The cost base for energy remodelling is determined by averaging the costs of actual projects and offers received,
- Linking the EPC translation tool to real energy pricing data,
- If the data is unavailable, a reasonable estimate of the thermal energy needed for primary energy and heating may be possible,
- The possibility to express preferences during the refurbishment process (e.g., eliminating certain building components, emphasizing primary energy, reducing CO₂ emissions, etc.),
- Life Cycle Analysis (LCA), a unique component that emphasises the benefits of refurbishment in accordance with the desired standard.

4.6 Support

The functionality and procedure for providing system user support are fully implemented in the system customer support module. Support for customers is achieved through the subsequent layers:

- User documentation,
- Technical documentation.

Every user interface needs to contain a "help" button that is prominently displayed. When the Help action is activated, a unique application window is opened that allows you to work and read the help material at the same time. A collection of papers organised logically into components and accessible via a dedicated help interface is called user documentation.

In order to see the documentation later without requiring the user to access the application interface, the interface must also enable the downloading of documentation in PDF format. The application's client will create the user manual, and the application's supplier will integrate it into the system.

The technical documentation has to include a minimum of:

- Revisions list including author and date of revision.
- Preface providing document specifics.
- A list of recorded faults together with debugging information.

4.7 Technical characteristics

Fundamental attributes of the central application layer:

- Web orientation: using a traditional web browser to access the system (needs additional software to be installed on the client PC),
- A more advanced user interface,
- The system's modular design allows for great scalability and system customisation.

Protecting the investment, minimizing the cost of investment, and maximizing system longevity should be the fundamental criteria for selecting the software that will be utilised in the creation of the application. Achieving these objectives requires a 100% share of open-source technologies.

Programming languages

The fundamental rules for selecting a programming language are as follows: it must be widely accepted in EU countries' higher education systems; additionally, because of the unique nature of the application, it must be multiplatform and allow for the use of open development tools. Similar requirements apply to the programming language: it needs to be widely used and have a sizable user base.

Similar to a "Opensource" library, a programming language needs to ensure longevity, be more than a decade old, and be constantly evolving.

The suggested programming language is JavaScript, also known as Phyton, and the suggested development tool is JavaScript Frameworks, also known as Django, which offers a full development environment.

Database

Additionally, databases must be open source, like:

- MySQL
- PostgreSQL
- Firebird
- GNU SQL Server
- SAP MaxDB
- ScimoreDB
- DXstoredatabasesystem
- HSQLDB
- CloudDB

Since MySQL is an open database, it is guaranteed to remain in the market for the next twenty years because of its commercial backing, which helps streamline the development process with no financial outlay.

Regardless of which database is used, an OBJECT-RELATIONAL-MAPPING (ORM) environment like Hibernate or something similar should be used for communication between databases and systems. This will allow for easy database replacement as well as data persistence and object access.

Application security

Using a WAF (Web application firewall) solution is required for a comprehensive and highly flexible solution to secure web applications and services. This kind of solution would offer proactive and thorough protection on the application layer against both general and targeted threats. Positive safety must be the guiding principle of the system, meaning that nothing can happen unless it is specifically authorised.

Because of this logic, the WAF can only reject requests that are legitimate and allowed, automatically defending vital web applications against intrusions. WAF must defend the system against a variety of application, infrastructure, and network attacks, including DOS, forcible browsing, cookie/session poisoning, SQL injection assaults, cross-site scripting, and parameter tampering.

To defend against all HTTP and HTTPS attacks, the WAF needs to include built-in rules. Although all components can be exported using open technologies, it is advised to employ commercial security solutions like Cisco or F5, given the sensitive nature of the region.

4.8 Language

The system must be able to operate in multiple languages. English must be utilised for the program's core solution, and it should be used during the application development process as well. The selected developer's national language must be used for all communications on the application's development.

The application supplier's task is to functionally integrate the translated text into the application; the customer of the application will supply the translated text into other languages.

4.9 Algorithm proposal

The assigned developer should define the algorithm (in the form of formulas, methods, and other "know-how"), perhaps in an Excel file. In addition to providing advice and clarification to a programmer lacking expertise in energy and other technical aspects, the service provider should take on the responsibility of overseeing and enhancing the recommendation calculation process. The algorithm example is shown in Table 8.

Table 8. The example of the Algorithm for development of an EPC translating tool

Step 1	Data Input Considering D2.5, D3.1, D3.2			
	Enter the information required for buildings, obtain data, and perhaps establish a connection with other databases holding more pertinent information and documents. Add additional information from building owners, such as a description of the overall condition of the building, information on its use and long-term objectives, and information from regional, national, and municipal strategy documents (particularly mandatory).			
Group	1st level	2nd level	Remarks	
Basic data (related to step 1)	Building designation		enter data	
	Name of the building		enter data	
	Location	City/Municipality		enter data
		Adress		
		Cadastral parcel		
	Type of building	Family House		choose between
		Apartment Building		
		Office Building		
		Kindergarten		
		Elementary School		
		High School		
		College/Faculty/University		
		Hospital		
		Health centre		
Hotel				
Restaurant				
Sports hall				
Commercial				

		Buildings for culture	enter data	
		Mixed use		
		Other non-residential		
	Dimensions	Number of floors		
		Gross area of the building (m ²)		
		Heated net area of the building (m ²)		
		Heated volume of the building (m ³)		
	Timeframe	Renovation		enter data
		Year of construction		
		Year of extension		
Year of reconstruction/renovation				
Other	Listed as cultural heritage	enter data		
Current state (related to step 1)	Usage	Number of functions	enter data	
		Number of people working in the building		
		Number of people using the building		
		Operational hours		
	Buildings envelope	Exterior walls	Utilise the energy audit and certificate data to add U for each component of the building envelope as well as a brief description of the sort of material and insulation that is currently in place.	
		Walls on border heated/unheated area		
		Walls to ground		
		Windows and doors (glazed) to exterior		
		Windows and doors (glazed) to unheated area		
		Windows and doors (not glazed) to exterior		
		Windows and doors (not glazed) to unheated area		
		Flat roofs		
		Pitched roofs		
		Ceilings to unheated attic		
		Ceilings above outside air		
		Ceilings on border heated/unheated area		
		Ground floors heated area		
		Ground floors unheated area		
	Technical systems	Heating	Usage information from energy audits and certificates, provide a brief description of the technical system's type, and indicate if it uses fossil fuels or non-fossil sources.	
		Cooling		
Hot water preparation				
Ventilation/Climatisation				
Lightning				
Solar powerplant				
Automation				
Remote measurement of energy and water consumption				

		Water installations	
	Energy Certificate	Issuance of Energy Certificates	Enter data
		Energy Certificate Date	
		Energy Class (Qhnd)	
		Energy Class (Eprim)	
		Qhnd (kWh)	
		Eprim (kWh)	
		Share of RES used for technical systems in Edel (%)	
		CO ₂ emissions (t)	
	Energy Consumption	Data on the energy used for heating, averaged over the last three years (kWh)	Input data (from the Energy Management Information System).
		Data on the use of electrical energy, averaged over the previous three years (kWh)	
		Data on the overall amount of energy consumed, the last three years, and the average (kWh)	
		Information about the building's overall energy use and heated areas, as well as the latest three years' averages (kWh/m ²)	
	Other	Seismic resistance	Add a brief comment Were any applied measures, analyses, identified necessary upgrades, etc. that have already been completed? (In Croatia, these initiatives are supported by RRF and ERDF funding, which comes from EU sources.)
		Fire protection	
		Accessibility for people with disabilities	
		Internal air quality	
		Moisture status	
		Smart and sustainable mobility	
		Green infrastructure	
		Nature based solutions	
	*create a list of further desired information, documents, and databases, subsequently explore potential ways to connect tools with them.		
Step 2	Data output Considering D2.5, D2.6, D3.3, D3.6, D5.1, D5.2		
	Using the instructions for the tool created in Task 4.2, analyse the buildings in the portfolio.		
Future state	Usage	Number of functions	Add data to the proposed intervention's scope.
		Number of people working in the building	
		Number of people using the building	
		Operational hours	
	Buildings envelope measures	Exterior walls	Software calculation The emphasis is on the most cost-effective combination of recommendations. To create BRP, the measures are prioritised.
		Walls on border heated/unheated area	
		Walls to ground	
		Windows and doors (glazed) to exterior	
		Windows and doors (glazed) to unheated area	
		Windows and doors (not glazed) to exterior	

		Windows and doors (not glazed) to unheated area	
		Flat roofs	
		Pitched roofs	
		Ceilings to unheated attic	
		Ceilings above outside air	
		Ceilings on border heated/unheated area	
		Ground floors heated area	
		Ground floors unheated area	
	Technical systems measures	Heating	
		Cooling	
		Hot water preparation	
		Ventilation/Climatization	
		Lightning	
		Solar powerplant	
		Automation	
		Remote measurement of energy and water consumption	
		Water installations	
	New Certificate (Estimation) Energy	Energy Certificate Designation	Software calculation / new reporting template
		Energy Certificate Date	
		Energy Class (Qhnd)	
		Energy Class (Eprim)	
		Qhnd (kWh)	
		Qhnd savings (kWh)	
		Eprim (kWh)	
		Eprim savings (kWh)	
		CO ₂ emissions (t)	
		Reduction of CO ₂ emissions (t)	
	New Consumption and Costs (Estimation) Energy	Data for energy for heating consumption, (kWh)	Software calculation
		Data for electrical energy consumption (kWh)	
		Data for total energy consumption (kWh)	
		Data for total energy consumption/heated area of the building, (kWh/m ²)	
	Other measures	Seismic resistance	Select and input data for each part's proposed intervention, along with a cost estimate
		Fire protection	
		Accessibility for people with disabilities	
		Internal air quality	
		Moisture status	
		Smart and sustainable mobility	

		Green infrastructure	Input the data, further organizing it according to situations, variants, and packages before selecting the best option or renovating the roadmap in harmony with BRP
		Nature based solutions	
	Summary	Total planned action	
		Estimated total cost	

5 Conclusions

This report includes a thorough overview of the requirements and steps needed to create a digital version of energy certificates. These include the calculator methodology, necessary programming, and necessary infrastructure. By presenting the results in an easy-to-understand manner, the deliverable will help end users realise the benefits of energy savings and be motivated to make investments and change their behaviour to use energy more wisely.

However, this report can be interpreted as an effort to raise the perceived value of EPCs among potential investors. The analysis was carried out by gathering prior research and/or examples of best practices, as well as by speaking with stakeholders to find out what information they believe should be included in the EPC or the EPC translating tool, and which is necessary to decide on a possible investment. This deliverable suggests standardised guidelines to be utilised throughout Europe and provides a set of instructions and guidelines on how to implement data required for investors in the next generation of EPCs.

Main outcomes of the tool could be defined as follows:

- A tool that is easy to use and **can be used by non-professionals**.
- **Recommendations first**: Cost-optimal combination of measures.
- The potential to examine multiple alternative measure combinations and compare investment costs and energy savings.
- **Prioritisation of measures** – connection with BRP.
- Easier building data entry with the option to freely enter real values.
- The base for energy renovation costs is the **average cost of actual projects**.
- The tool's link to information on **actual energy prices**.
- If data are unavailable, it may be possible to approximate the amount of heat energy needed for primary energy and heating.
- Ability to set preferences through the renovation process (focus on primary energy, focus on CO₂ emissions or others).
- Using life cycle analysis (LCA) as a unique component to emphasise the advantages of renewal.

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